

ELECTRONIC MARKETING TOOLS AND MARKETING PERFORMANCE OF FIRST BANK PLC IN UYO METROPOLIS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18622612>

Abstract: Despite the growing potential of electronic marketing (e-marketing), First Bank PLC in Uyo Metropolis has faced challenges in fully leveraging its digital marketing strategies. A pilot study revealed several specific issues, including inconsistent engagement with online customers, limited personalization of marketing messages, and underutilization of search engine marketing (SEM), search engine optimization (SEO), social media marketing, and email marketing. To this end, the study examined the effect of electronic marketing tools on the marketing performance of First Bank PLC in Uyo metropolis. Specifically, the study sought to: examine the effect of search engine marketing (SEM) and content marketing on the marketing performance of First Bank PLC. Data from 398 respondents from a population of 71,312 were collected with survey research technique as the research design. Electronic Marketing and Marketing Performance Questionnaire was used to obtain data for the study. Analysis of data was done through the use of frequency tables, simple percentages, while hypotheses were tested using simple regression analysis. Findings revealed that the two variable of electronic marketing tools; search engine marketing and content marketing have significant effect on the marketing performance of First Bank PLC. The study concluded that there is a significant effect of electronic marketing tools on marketing performance of First Bank PLC in Uyo metropolis. The researchers recommended among others; that First Bank should create and share content such as blogs, videos, and infographics that address customers' financial needs and concerns, such as budgeting tips, loan application guides, and investment strategies in order to attract and engage potential customers, strengthening brand trust and loyalty.

Keywords: Electronic marketing tool, marketing performance, SEM, SEO, Social media marketing and email marketing

Introduction

In an era marked by rapid technological advancements, globalization, and intense market competition, electronic marketing (e-marketing) has emerged as a crucial tool for businesses to reach and engage with their target audiences. E-marketing applies marketing principle in the internet to source for, engage and sustain transaction relationships (Mfon & Macaulay, 2023; Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019). This approach encompasses a wide

array of strategies including mobile banking apps, online banking, Automated Teller Machines (ATMs), email marketing, and social media, all aimed at leveraging the internet's power to reach consumers more efficiently than traditional methods.

E-marketing is the use of digital technologies and platforms to promote and sell products and services. This includes the use of websites, email, social media, and online advertising to reach and engage with customers. Through e-marketing, businesses can target specific audiences and measure the effectiveness of their promotional efforts in real-time (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019). E-marketing encompasses strategies that facilitate interaction between businesses and customers through online channels. This involves engaging customers via social media, blogs, and online forums to build relationships, gather feedback, and enhance customer experience. This engagement helps companies understand customer needs and preferences better (Kotler & Keller, 2016). E-marketing involves utilizing data analytics to inform marketing strategies and decisions. By analysing customer behaviour, preferences, and engagement metrics, businesses can tailor their marketing efforts to improve targeting, personalization, and overall effectiveness. This data-driven approach enables more precise and effective marketing strategies (Ryan, 2016).

Marketing performance is the measurement of the effectiveness and efficiency of marketing activities. It involves evaluating various metrics such as return on investment (ROI), customer lifetime value (CLV), customer acquisition cost (CAC), and conversion rates, as key performance indicators (KPI), to determine how well marketing tools achieve the set objectives (Clark, 2020). These metrics provide a quantitative basis for understanding how marketing efforts impact on a business's bottom line (Sola & Victoria, 2024). Customer acquisition cost (CAC) is a critical metric that calculates the incurred cost of acquiring a new customer. It includes dividing the sales and marketing expenses by the total acquired customers during a specified period of time. A lower CAC indicates higher efficiency of marketing tools. Customer lifetime value (CLV), on the other hand, serves as the estimate of a particular customer's total purchases made in the company over the customer's lifetime. Balancing CAC and CLV is crucial for sustainable growth (Farris, 2020).

The link between electronic marketing and marketing performance is significant and multifaceted. E-Marketing tools have the potential to enhance marketing performance by providing more precise targeting, personalization, and real-time engagement with consumers. Digital platforms offer advanced analytics tools for a business to follow-up on, track and measure the effectiveness of its marketing efforts, leading to data-driven decision-making and continuous optimization (Kingsnorth, 2019). One of the key benefits of e-Marketing is its ability to reach a broader and more diverse audience at a lower cost compared to traditional marketing methods. This expanded reach can lead to higher customer acquisition rates and improved brand visibility. The interactive nature of digital platforms allows for immediate feedback and engagement, enabling businesses to adapt their tools quickly in response to consumer behaviour and preferences (Ryan, 2024).

This study focused on electronic marketing tools and marketing performance with specific aspects of electronic marketing such as search engine marketing (SEM) and content marketing as proxies. First Bank PLC in Uyo Metropolis was the area of coverage of the research. Customers of the Bank participated as respondents in the research. This study is significant as it would provide a comprehensive analysis of how e-marketing tools affect the marketing performance of First Bank Plc, offering valuable insights for both academic and practical applications. For academic purposes, it contributes to the existing literature on e-marketing and its efficacy in the banking sector, particularly within the Nigerian context, which is under-researched. Practically, the findings will aid marketing managers and decision-makers at First Bank PLC in understanding the effectiveness of their current

e-marketing strategies, enabling them to make data-driven decisions to enhance customer engagement, satisfaction, and retention.

Also, it would be an invaluable tool for students, academics and Nigerian public as it explores the relationship between electronic marketing and marketing performance and in the survival of the education sector of Nigerian economy as a whole. More so, this work will provide accessible data for future research, as it will add value to existing body of knowledge.

Statement of the problem

In today's digital landscape, where seamless online interactions are essential for business success, electronic marketing should ideally drive substantial growth. By leveraging social media marketing, search engine marketing (SEM), email marketing, and content marketing, businesses can enhance customer acquisition, improve retention, and build strong brand loyalty. These tools, when used effectively, offer the potential to boost market share and profitability, positioning companies for long-term success.

Despite the growing potential of electronic marketing (e-marketing), First Bank PLC in Uyo Metropolis has faced challenges in fully leveraging its digital marketing tools. A pilot study carried out by the researcher with a cross section of First Bank PLC employees in July (2024) revealed several specific issues, including inconsistent engagement with online customers, limited personalization of marketing messages, and underutilization of social media marketing, search engine marketing (SEM), email marketing, and content marketing. These challenges have hindered the bank's ability to effectively reach and retain customers, resulting in lower customer satisfaction, missed revenue opportunities, and a diminished competitive edge in the digital marketplace.

This research aimed to address these issues by providing empirical evidence on the effectiveness of these e-marketing tools, specifically SEM, SEO, social media marketing, and email marketing, in improving marketing performance. By focusing on the findings from the pilot study, the research would offer actionable insights into how First Bank PLC can optimize its digital marketing tools to enhance customer engagement, increase satisfaction, and ultimately drive better marketing outcomes. The study would evaluate the effect of these e-marketing tools on the bank's overall marketing performance in the Uyo Metropolis and provide recommendations to improve their implementation. Therefore, the specific objects the study pursued were;

- i. Examine the effect of search engine marketing (SEM) on the marketing performance of First Bank PLC in Uyo metropolis.
- ii. Examine the effect of content marketing on the marketing performance of First Bank PLC in Uyo metropolis.

Research questions

- i. What is the effect of search engine marketing (SEM) on the marketing performance of First Bank PLC in Uyo metropolis?
- ii. What is the effect of content marketing on the marketing performance of First Bank PLC in Uyo metropolis?

Research hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant effect of search engine marketing (SEM) on the marketing performance of First Bank PLC in Uyo metropolis.

H₀₂: Content marketing has no significant effect on the marketing performance of First Bank PLC in Uyo metropolis.

Review of Literature Review

Conceptual framework

A conceptual model was developed to assess how electronic marketing tools (as the independent variable), relate with marketing performance (as dependent variable). The model indicates that marketing performance is influenced by electronic marketing tools proxies namely, social media marketing, search engine marketing (SEM), email marketing, and content marketing. Below is the diagrammatic presentation of the researchers’ conceptual model:

Figure 1: A Conceptual Model showing the relationship between electronic marketing tools and marketing performance

Source: Researchers’ Conceptualization 2024

Concept of electronic marketing

Marketing efforts that focus on the use of electronic devices to attract, reach and maintain potential and current customers is electronic marketing, or e-marketing. It leverages digital channels such as search engines, social media, email, and websites to reach a wide audience and promote products or services (Adama & Yusuff, 2021). Key components of e-marketing include search engine marketing (SEM), content marketing, pay-per-click (PPC) advertising, social media marketing and email marketing, each contributing to a comprehensive strategy to attract and engage consumers (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019). The rise of mobile technology and data analytics has further enhanced e-marketing capabilities, enabling personalized and real-time marketing efforts. This digital approach not only broadens market reach but also allows for more precise targeting and measurement of marketing effectiveness (Ryan, 2016, Uford, 2018).

Uford, et al. (2022) stated that “e-marketing involved the use of digital technologies including but not limited to the internet to achieve the marketing goals of the company, more freely and easily than in traditional marketing methods”. According to Macaulay and Mfon (2023), e-marketing is “the application of social media platforms and company websites to attract and retain customers, and enhance sales and corporate image of businesses”. E-marketing's effectiveness hinges on its ability to collect and analyze vast amounts of data, enabling businesses to tailor their strategies to individual consumer preferences and behaviours. Tools like social media insights, Google Analytics, and customer relationship management (CRM) systems provide valuable insights into customer interactions and trends, allowing for more informed decision-making (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019). Moreover, the interactive nature of digital platforms facilitates linear dialogue between consumers and brands,

resulting in strengthened interactions and enhancing customer loyalty (Kotler et al., 2017). E-marketing also offers cost advantages over traditional marketing methods, as digital campaigns can be scaled and adjusted with relative ease and minimal expense. The adaptability and scalability of e-marketing strategies ensure that businesses of all sizes can compete in the digital marketplace, promoting innovation and growth (Todor, 2016). For the purpose of this study, we define electronic marketing as the use of digital channels and technologies such as mobile banking apps, online banking, and social media marketing to promote and sell products or services.

Search engine marketing (SEM)

Search Engine is a powerful digital strategy that focuses on increasing website visibility on search engine results pages (SERPs) through advertising. Businesses use this approach to bid for ad placements on keywords relevant to their offerings, which drives potential customers to their websites (Musa & Jimoh, 2019). The strategy relies on a pay-per-click (PPC) model, charging companies each time a user clicks an ad. This cost-effective approach is designed to target audiences with high intent, making it valuable for businesses seeking measurable and immediate results (Bako & Babajide, 2022). Keyword selection and bidding are central to Search Engine Marketing, especially within Google Ads, where an auction-based system determines ad placement. Factors such as the bid amount and ad quality score determine where ads appear, with higher-quality ads achieving better visibility at a lower cost. This setup allows businesses to optimize ad relevance and budget efficiency, reaching users actively searching for related products or services (Udoh & Edet, 2021). The researcher' define search engine marketing (SEM) as the “bank's strategy of using paid advertising on search engines like Google or Bing to attract potential customers who are searching for specific financial products or services (e.g., loans, savings accounts, credit cards).”

Content marketing

Content marketing is “a strategic approach focused on creating and distributing valuable, relevant, and consistent content to attract and retain a clearly defined audience, thereby aiming to drive profitable customer action by offering information that meets the needs or interests of potential customers, rather than pushing direct sales messages” (Gruber & Schlegelmilch, 2023). This form of marketing builds trust and loyalty, positioning a brand as a reliable source of knowledge within its industry, which ultimately fosters stronger customer relationships (Baum & Kabst, 2019). A meaningful content marketing originates with an understanding of the preferences of the target consumers, including their challenges, and interests. By conducting research, businesses can create personal fictional representations of ideal customers that guide content creation. Tailoring content to address specific pain points and aspirations not only improves engagement but also increases the likelihood of conversions as customers find genuine value in the information presented (Sullivan & De Meyer, 2020). The researchers define content marketing as referring to “a strategic approach focused on creating, distributing, and sharing valuable, relevant, and consistent content online to attract and engage a target audience.”

Concept of marketing performance

Marketing performance refers to the measurement and evaluation of the effectiveness and efficiency of marketing activities in achieving organizational objectives (Uford, 2017, Akpan et al, 2022; Macaulay & Mfon, 2023). This includes analyzing various metrics and key performance indicators (KPIs) such as customer acquisition cost (CAC), return on investment (ROI), conversion rates, and customer lifetime value (CLV) to determine the success of marketing strategies and campaigns (Farris et al., 2020). Effective marketing performance assessment helps businesses understand what is working, spot out the aspects that need improvement, and then optimize their

marketing efforts by making data-driven decisions. Ekong et al (2022), assert that assessment of SMEs' performance is very important as these SMEs are the economic pillars of many nations and continents.

Techniques for measuring marketing performance include the use of analytics tools, performance dashboards, and regular reporting, enabling marketers to track progress and adjust strategies in real-time (Pauwels, 2015). According to Akpan, Mfon and Ibok (2022), "marketing performance involves aligning marketing team's goals to actual results. It is measured using such indicators as revenues and sales, lead generation, customer retention, brand awareness and engagement. However, the indicator or metric used is dependent on a marketer's core objectives and plan."

For the purpose of the study, the researchers define marketing performance as the effectiveness of a company's marketing activities in achieving business objectives, measured through various metrics such as sales revenue, market share, return on investment (ROI), customer acquisition cost (CAC), customer retention rate, customer lifetime value (CLV), lead conversion rate, brand awareness, customer satisfaction, and engagement metrics.

Electronic marketing tools and marketing performance

Electronic marketing (e-marketing) significantly impacts marketing performance by leveraging digital channels to enhance customer reach, engagement, and satisfaction, leading to improved sales and brand loyalty. Studies highlight that e-marketing tools, such as search engine optimization, and social media marketing, can drive better marketing performance by enabling personalized communication and real-time customer feedback (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019). In the Nigerian context, research by Nwaizugbo and Anukam (2024) demonstrates that businesses adopting e-marketing techniques witness increased market share and competitive advantage due to the growing internet penetration and mobile phone usage. Okoli (2020) underscores that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria benefit significantly from e-marketing by reducing costs and accessing broader markets, which ultimately enhances their marketing performance.

Search engine marketing (SEM) and marketing performance

Obi and Ekeh (2022) examined the impact of search engine marketing (SEM) on marketing performance at Jumia Nigeria. The study showed a significant positive relationship between SEM and marketing performance, particularly in website traffic and sales conversions. Nnamdi and Esther (2022) analyzed the effects of search engine marketing on marketing performance at Zenith Bank PLC in Lagos. Findings revealed that effective search engine marketing increased online visibility and enhanced brand awareness. Adams and Ogundele (2022) investigated the impact of search engine marketing on marketing performance at GTBank. The study found that search engine marketing had a substantial positive effect on marketing performance, particularly in lead generation and customer engagement. Chika and Oluwaseun (2024) examined the relationship between search engine marketing and marketing performance at Konga in Nigeria. The study found that search engine marketing strategies, including pay-per-click (PPC) campaigns, significantly boosted customer retention and sales performance.

Content marketing and marketing performance

Chijioke and Fatima (2021) examined the relationship between content marketing and marketing performance among young consumers in Nigeria, with a focus on Jumia Nigeria. The findings revealed a strong positive relationship between content marketing efforts via influencer collaborations and enhanced marketing performance, particularly in fostering brand loyalty. Kelechi and Bola (2022) investigated the role of content marketing in enhancing marketing performance at Access Bank PLC in Port Harcourt. The findings revealed a significant positive correlation between effective content marketing efforts and improved marketing performance

metrics. Adebayo and Nneka (2023) investigated the impact of content marketing strategies on marketing performance at First Bank Nigeria in Lagos. The findings indicated that interactive content marketing techniques significantly enhanced marketing performance through increased customer engagement.

Theoretical framework

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) by Davis (1989)

This model, Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Davis in 1989, highlights the two basic factors that popularise the use and acceptance of technology to be perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. Davis' argument is that people readily adopt any technology they perceive as relevant, easy to use and beneficial. This model has been widely applied to various technological innovations, including electronic marketing tools. For instance, in the context of banking, TAM explains how customers perceive and engage with digital marketing platforms such as online banking services, mobile apps, and email marketing campaigns (Davis, 1989).

In the study of First Bank PLC's marketing performance electronic-marketing in Uyo Metropolis, TAM is particularly relevant as it provides a framework to assess customer acceptance of the bank's digital marketing strategies. By evaluating the perceived ease of use and usefulness of these digital tools, the study can determine their impact on customer engagement and overall marketing performance. For example, if customers find the bank's online marketing efforts intuitive and valuable, they are more likely to interact with these platforms, potentially leading to improved customer retention and satisfaction (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000).

The Diffusion of Innovations Theory by Rogers (1962)

The Diffusion of Innovations Theory, formulated by Rogers (1962), explores how new ideas and technologies spread within a social system. The theory identifies several key factors influencing the adoption of innovations, including the perceived attributes of communication channels, innovation, the social system, and the rate of adoption. Readily diffusion occurs when innovations that are seen to be of advantage, easy to use and compatible with existing values. This model has served in enhancing a better understanding on how technological innovations are adopted and utilized across various sectors (Rogers, 1962).

In the context of First Bank PLC's electronic marketing strategies in Uyo Metropolis, Diffusion of Innovations Theory is particularly useful for examining how new digital marketing tools are adopted by customers. By analyzing how these innovations are perceived by the bank's clientele and the factors influencing their adoption, the study can assess the effectiveness and reach of the bank's electronic marketing initiatives. For example, understanding the rate of adoption and the barriers faced by customers in using digital banking services can provide insights into the overall impact of these innovations on marketing performance and customer engagement (Moore & Benbasat, 1991).

Review of empirical studies

This section examined existing empirical studies that investigated the effect of electronic marketing tools on marketing performance. The studies reviewed provided valuable insights into how electronic marketing tools such as social media marketing (SMM), search engine marketing (SEM), content marketing and e-mail marketing impact return on investment (ROI), sales growth, customer acquisition cost, customer retention rate, and marketing performance.

Usman and Lawal (2021) examined the relationship between Electronic Marketing and Marketing Performance in the retail sector at Spar Nigeria, in Kano. The study engaged a descriptive research design with a sample of 180 respondents. Findings from regression analysis revealed a positive correlation between digital marketing usage and consumer purchase rates. Recommendations included enhancing email marketing and social media

presence to sustain customer engagement. However, the population of the study and the method of data collection were not mentioned.

Okeke and Maduka (2021) investigated Electronic Marketing and its impacts on Marketing Performance at GTBank in Port Harcourt. Employing a mixed-method approach, the population of the study was 535, the study surveyed 250 respondents. Data were analyzed using regression analysis, revealing that the adoption of digital marketing channels led to higher customer interaction and sales conversions. The researchers recommended that GTBank should further develop digital strategies to enhance market reach. Critically point of view, the study the population of the study and the method of data collection was not mentioned.

Olu and Banjo (2021) explored the effect of electronic marketing on the marketing performance of PEP Stores in Ibadan. Utilizing a sample of 190 respondents, the study employed SPSS for data analysis. The findings revealed a positive relationship between digital marketing activities and improved brand visibility. The study suggested that PEP Stores should invest in influencer partnerships to enhance marketing outcomes further. However, the study could have been strengthened by incorporating qualitative insights to provide a deeper understanding of the mechanisms behind the observed association and by expanding the sample size for greater generalizability.

Emeka and Nwosu (2021) investigated the influence of electronic marketing on the marketing performance of Zenith Insurance in Port Harcourt. The study surveyed 260 respondents and analyzed the data using regression models. Results indicated a strong positive correlation between online marketing channels and client acquisition rates. The study recommended enhancing visibility through search engine optimization (SEO) and paid advertisements. However, the research would have benefited from examining the cost-effectiveness of these strategies and exploring potential challenges organizations face when implementing online marketing techniques.

Kelechi and Adaobi (2021) evaluated the effect of electronic marketing on the marketing performance of First Bank Nigeria. Adopting a quasi-experimental design, the study examined a population of 600 bank customers and analyzed responses from a sample of 250, selected through simple random sampling. Data were analyzed using ANOVA, revealing that electronic marketing strategies positively influenced marketing performance, particularly in customer acquisition and brand loyalty. The study concluded that First Bank should enhance its electronic marketing initiatives by prioritizing personalized digital experiences and optimizing online customer service. It also recommended incorporating mobile marketing and leveraging data analytics for improved customer insights. However, the study could have been enriched by considering the impact of external factors, such as market competition and customer digital literacy, which may mediate the effectiveness of electronic marketing strategies.

Methodology of the Research

Research Design

Descriptive research design allows independent variables to be examined in relations to the dependent variable by assessing and analyzing the opinions of the participants of a study. Therefore, the design was seen as suitable to be used for this study.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised all customers of First Bank PLC, Udo Udoma, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State which was 71,312. The population was deemed to be known, as it was drawn from the office of the manager of First Bank PLC, PLC, Udo Udoma in Uyo, via their Business Object software application (Office of the Manager, 2024).

Sample Size Determination

The sample size was determined using Taro Yamani formula as follows;

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = Sample size

N= Population size == 71,312.

e = Margin of errors = 5% = 0.05

Hence:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{71,312}{1+71,312. (0.05)^2} \\ &= \frac{71,312}{1+178.28} \\ &= \frac{71,312}{179.3} = 397.7 \\ & \quad n = 398 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, 398 was the sample size,

Sampling Technique

The convenience sampling technique was used for the study. The choice of this technique was to make the data collection process straightforward and less time-consuming. To apply this method, respondents were selected based on their availability and willingness to participate in the study. Specifically, participants who were easily accessible within the research area were approached during peak hours of business activity, ensuring a sample that reflected the typical customer base. This approach allowed the researcher to collect data from individuals who were readily available, without the need for extensive pre-planning or travel.

Method of data Collection

In conducting this research work, relevant primary data were collected from customers of First Bank PLC., in Uyo metropolis through the use of questionnaire titled Electronic Marketing and Marketing Performance Questionnaire (EMMPQ) (Appendix 1). The questionnaire was sent as a Microsoft link to the emails and Whatsapp numbers of respondents.

Validity of the Research Instrument

The questionnaire that served as the instrument for data collection was developed and used by the researchers. Based on the research objectives, relevant statements were framed to reflect the content of the study. The validity of the content was ensured by the research supervisors who guided the work. They assessed the questionnaire statements to determine if the variables and the formulated objectives were actually captured. An independent evaluator equally assessed the questionnaire instrument. With the corrections and valuable contributions of the various assessors, the instrument was corrected, realigned and proven fit to measure what it was set to measure.

Reliability of Research Instrument

The reliability was determined through the test-re-test reliability technique. Copies of the questionnaire were administered to 14 respondents who were randomly selected. After a period of 12 days, the same questionnaire were re-administered to the same respondents. The Cronbach (Alpha) model was employed to test the reliability

of the instrument used in the survey. A Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of 0.668 was achieved (see Appendix 2)

Variables and their Measures

Search Engine Marketing: The variable was measured using adjusted Gupta (2018) 4 item scale. Responses on a four point Likert scale ranged from (1) strongly disagree to (4) strongly agree. Examples of items measuring search engine is “We utilize search engines to drive more online transactions for First Bank PLC”.

Content Marketing: The variable was measured using adjusted Farris (2020) 4 item content marketing questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed using a four point Likert scale. Responses ranged from (1) strongly disagree to (4) strongly agree. An example of an item is, “First Bank’s content marketing strategies help increase the visibility of First Bank PLC in Uyo Metropolis”. The Cronbach's alpha value for this scale was 74.

Marketing Performance: The variables was measured using adjusted Todor (2016) 4 item marketing performance questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed using a four point Likert scale. Responses ranged from (1) strongly disagreed to (4) strongly agreed. An example of marketing performance item is, “Search engines have contributed to an increase in online transactions for First Bank PLC” The Cronbach's alpha value for this scale was 74.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Questionnaire Administration

Table 1: Number of Questionnaire Administered and Returned

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Total number administered	398	100
Total number returned	313	78.6
Non response rate	85	21.4

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 1 shows that 313(78.6%) of the total questionnaire distributed were returned, while 85(19.1%) were not returned. Thus, 313 (80.9%) of the distributed questionnaires were in useable form for analysis.

Distribution of Questionnaire Responses

Table 2: Percentage analysis of the Responses on Search Engine (SE)

Search Engine (SE)					Total
	SA	A	D	SD	
Search engines increase the visibility of First Bank Plc in Uyo Metropolis.	88 (28.1%)	123 (39.3%)	60 (19.2%)	42 (13.4%)	313 (100%)
Search engine optimization (SEO) improves customer engagement with First Bank Plc’s online platforms.	110 (35.1%)	89 (28.4%)	44 (14.1%)	70 (22.4%)	313 (100%)
Search engines drive more online transactions for First Bank Plc.	152 (48.6%)	74 (23.6%)	62 (19.8%)	25 (8.0%)	313 (100%)
Search engines enhance the brand awareness of First Bank Plc among potential customers in Uyo Metropolis.	130 (41.5%)	96 (30.7%)	63 (20.1%)	24 (7.7%)	313 (100%)

Total	480	382	229	161	1252
Proportion of N	120	96	57	40	313
Percentage of Proportion	(38.3%)	(30.5%)	(18.3%)	(12.9%)	(100%)

Source: Field survey 2025

Table 2 shows the frequency of responses and their percentages on the search engine (SE) dimension of a proportion of 313 respondents, 88(28.1%) of the respondents strongly agreed that search engine increase the visibility of First Bank in Uyo Metropolis; 123(39.3%) agreed; 60(19.2%) disagreed; while 42(13.4%) strongly disagreed. Also, 110(35.1%) strongly agreed that Search engine optimization (SEO) improves customer engagement with First Bank Plc’s online platforms; 89(28.4%) agreed; 44(14.1%) disagreed; while 70(22.4%) strongly disagreed. Equally, 152 (48.6%) of the respondents strongly agreed that Search engines drive more online transactions for First Bank Plc.; 74(23.6%) agreed; 62(19.8%) disagreed; while 25(8.0%) strongly disagreed. Finally, 130(41.5%) of the respondents strongly agreed that Search engines enhance the brand awareness of First Bank Plc among potential customers in Uyo Metropolis; .agreed; 63(20.1%) disagreed; while 24(7.7%) strongly disagreed. Meanwhile, 120 (38.3%) strongly agreed to the statements, 57 (18.3%) disagreed while 24 (7.7%) strongly disagreed.

Table 3: Percentage analysis of the Responses on Content Marketing

Content Marketing					Total
	SA	A	D	SD	
First Bank’s content marketing strategies help increase the visibility of First Bank Plc in Uyo Metropolis.	100 (31.9%)	111 (35.5%)	78 (24.9%)	24 (7.7%)	313 (100%)
First Bank’s content marketing efforts enhance customer engagement with First Bank Plc’s online platforms.	150 (47.9%)	69 (22.1%)	42 (13.4%)	52 (16.6%)	313 (100%)
First Bank’s content marketing strategies drive more online transactions for First Bank Plc	122 (39.0%)	113 (36.1%)	64 (20.4%)	14 (4.5%)	313 (100%)
First Bank’s content marketing initiatives help build stronger brand awareness for First Bank Plc in Uyo Metropolis	100 (31.9%)	111 (35.5%)	78 (24.9%)	24 (7.7%)	313 (100%)
Total	472	404	262	114	1252
Proportion of N	118	101	66	28	313
Percentage of Proportion	(37.7%)	(32.3%)	(20.9%)	(9.1%)	(100%)

Source: Field survey 2025

Table 3 shows the frequency of responses and their percentages on content marketing dimension of a proportion of 313 respondents, 100(31.9%) of the respondents strongly agreed that First Bank’s content marketing strategies help increase the visibility of First Bank Plc in Uyo Metropolis.; 111(35.5%) agreed; 78(24.9%) disagreed; while 24(7.7%) strongly disagreed. Also, 150(47.9%) strongly agreed that First Bank’s content marketing efforts enhance customer engagement with First Bank Plc’s online platforms; 69(22.1%) agreed; 42(13.4%) disagreed; while 52(16.6%) strongly disagreed. Equally, 122 (39.0%) of the respondents strongly agreed that First Bank’s

content marketing strategies drive more online transactions for First Bank Plc; 113(36.1%) agreed; 64(20.4%) were undecided; 14(4.5%) disagreed; while 14(4.5%) strongly disagreed. Finally, 100(31.9%) of the respondents strongly agreed that First Bank’s content marketing initiatives help build stronger brand awareness for First Bank Plc in Uyo Metropolis; 111(35.5%) agreed; 78(24.9%) disagreed; while 24(7.7%) strongly disagreed. Meanwhile, 118 (37.7%) strongly agreed to the statements, 101 (32.3%) agreed, 66 (20.9%) disagreed while 28 (9.1%) strongly disagreed.

Table 4: Percentage analysis of the Responses on Marketing Performance

Marketing Performance					
	SA	A	D	SD	Total
I often discover First Bank’s products and services through search engine results	98 (31.3%)	113 (36.1%)	78 (24.9%)	24 (7.7%)	313 (100%)
I am more likely to patronize First Bank after reading their value-driven content online.	140 (44.7%)	79 (25.2%)	42 (13.4%)	52 (16.6%)	313 (100%)
I have recommended First Bank to others after engaging with their social media posts.	112 (35.8%)	123 (39.2%)	64 (20.4%)	14 (4.5%)	313 (100%)
I have returned to use First Bank’s services after receiving follow-up emails.	90 (28.7%)	121 (38.7%)	78 (24.9%)	24 (7.7%)	313 (100%)
Total	440	436	262	114	1252
Proportion of N	110	109	66	28	313
Percentage of Proportion	(35.2%)	(34.8%)	(20.9%)	(9.1%)	(100%)

Source: Field survey 2025

Table 4 shows the frequency of responses and their percentages on marketing performance dimension. From a proportion of 313 respondents, 98(31.3%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they often discover First Bank’s products and services through search engine results; 113(36.1%) agreed; 78(24.9%) disagreed; while 24(7.7%) strongly disagreed. Also, 140(44.7%) strongly agreed that they am more likely to patronize First Bank after reading their value-driven content online; 79(25.2%) agreed; 42(13.4%) disagreed; while 52(16.6%) strongly disagreed. Equally, 112 (35.8%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they have recommended First Bank to others after engaging with their social media posts; 123(39.2%) agreed; 64(20.4%) were undecided; 14(4.5%) disagreed; while 14(4.5%) strongly disagreed. Finally, 90(28.7%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they have returned to use First Bank’s services after receiving follow-up emails; 121(38.7%) agreed; 78(24.9%) disagreed; while 24(7.7%) strongly disagreed. Meanwhile, 110 (35.2%) strongly agreed to questions, 109 (34.8%) agreed, 66 (20.9%) disagreed while 28 (9.1%) strongly disagreed.

Test of hypotheses

The decision rule for test of hypotheses was determined thus:

If the calculated t-value is greater than or equal to the critical

T-value, the null hypothesis will be rejected and the alternative hypothesis will be accepted; if the calculated t-value is less than the critical t-value, the null hypothesis will be accepted and the alternative hypothesis will be rejected.

Hypothesis One

Ho₁: There is no significant effect of search engine marketing (SEM) on the marketing performance of First Bank PLC in Uyo metropolis.

Independent Variable: Search Engine Marketing (SEM)

Dependent Variable: Marketing Performance

Simple regression analysis was used to analysis the data in order to determine the relationship between the variables using Statistical Package Social Science (SPSS version 21).

Table 5:

Model Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of the Influence of Search Engine on Marketing Performance of First Bank PLC In Uyo

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.677 ^a	.569	.565	1.43233

Predictors: (Constant), Search_Engine_Mark.

From the result in Table 5 and Appendix 3, R-square of the regression analysis is .569. This finding suggests that 56.9% of the variance in marketing performance is explained by search engine marketing variables. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) confirmed the existence of a positive significant impact and the study found that the regression model is best fit for predicting the relationship between search engine marketing and marketing performance [F = 476.638, t = 8.532 and p<0.05]. Given this result, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is positive and significant effect of search engine on marketing performance of First Bank PLC in Uyo metropolis. Similarly, the study revealed that every unit change in search engine marketing would cause a variance of 87.7% in marketing performance (Beta= .677, p=0.000).

Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: Content marketing has no significant effect on the marketing performance of First Bank PLC in Uyo metropolis.

Independent Variable: Content Marketing

Dependent Variable: Marketing Performance

Simple regression Analysis was used to analysis the data in order to determine the relationship between the variables using Statistical Package Social Science (SPSS version 21).

Table 6:Model Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of the Influence Of Content Marketing on Marketing Performance of First Bank PLC in Uyo.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.622 ^a	.475	.474	.55520

a. Predictors: (Constant), Conte_Marke.

From the result in Table 6 and Appendix 4, R-square of the regression analysis is .475. This finding suggests that 47.5 % of the variance in marketing performance is explained by content marketing variables. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) confirmed the existence of a positive significant impact and the study found that the regression model is best fit for predicting the relationship between content marketing and marketing performance [F = 62.587, t = 12.827and p<0.05]. Given this result, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, content marketing has a significant effect on marketing performance of First Bank PLC in Uyo metropolis. Similarly, the study

revealed that every unit change in content marketing would cause a variance of 62.2% in marketing performance in the 21st century (Beta= .622, p=0.000).

Discussion of Findings

Search Engine Marketing (SEM) and Marketing Performance

The result of the study shows that there is a positive and strong significant relationship between the variables under study with correction ($r = .677$). This implies that the visibility of First Bank on search engines has increased customer's awareness of its products. That is to say that the result established that search engine marketing (SEM) will effect marketing performance of First Bank PLC in Uyo metropolis. This result is in support of the study and findings of Ajayi and Olamide (2023) who examined the impact of search engine marketing (SEM) on marketing performance at Jumia Nigeria. The study showed a significant positive relationship between SEM and marketing performance, particularly in website traffic and sales conversions. The result is also in support of the study and findings of Nkem and Eze (2022) who analyzed the effects of search engine marketing on marketing performance at Zenith Bank PLC in Lagos. Findings revealed that effective search engine marketing increased online visibility and enhanced brand awareness.

The second objective was to examine the effect of content marketing on the marketing performance of First Bank PLC in Uyo metropolis. The result of the study shows that there is a positive and strong significant relationship between the variables under study with correction ($r = .622$). This implies that the informative content shared by First Bank has increased customer's interest in their products and services. That is to say that the result established that the content marketing will affect marketing performance of First Bank PLC in Uyo metropolis. This result is in support of the study and findings of Chijioke and Fatima (2021) who examined the relationship between content marketing and marketing performance among young consumers in Nigeria, with a focus on Jumia Nigeria. The findings revealed a strong positive relationship between content marketing efforts via influencer collaborations and enhanced marketing performance, particularly in fostering brand loyalty. The result is in support of the study and findings of Kelechi and Bola (2022) who investigated the role of content marketing in enhancing marketing performance at Access Bank PLC in Port Harcourt. The findings revealed a significant positive correlation between effective content marketing efforts and improved marketing performance metrics.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were made:

- i Search Engine marketing (SEM) has a significant effect on the marketing performance of First Bank PLC in Uyo metropolis.
- ii Content marketing has a significant effect on the marketing performance of First Bank PLC in Uyo metropolis.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, First Bank PLC in Uyo metropolis should implement the following recommendations:

- i The bank should produce high-quality, informative content tailored to customer needs, such as blogs, FAQs, and video tutorials about banking products and services. In order to boost the website's search engine ranking and enhance marketing performance.
- ii First Bank should create and share content such as blogs, videos, and infographics that address customers' financial needs and concerns, such as budgeting tips, loan application guides, and investment strategies in order to attract and engage potential customers, strengthening brand trust and loyalty.

Contributions to Knowledge

i This study provides empirical data on the relationship between electronic marketing tools (mobile banking apps, online banking, and social media marketing) and marketing performance in the banking sector, specifically within First Bank PLC in Uyo Metropolis.

ii This research offers localized insights on how digital marketing strategies influence customer engagement and retention in the Nigerian banking industry, helping financial institutions tailor their marketing strategies.

Suggestion for Further Research

Future research should compare the effectiveness of e-marketing tools in different industries, such as manufacturing companies, retail, and telecommunications, to determine best practices and sector-specific strategies.

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APPENDIX 1

Electronic Marketing and Marketing Performance Questionnaire

Please respond to the following research related statements by ticking in the appropriate box. Select only one response per statement

SA = **Strongly Agree,**

A = **Agree**

D = **Disagree**

SD = **Strongly Disagree**

S/N	VARIABLES	OPTIONS			
	Search Engine (SE)	SA	A	D	D
1	Search engines increase the visibility of First Bank Plc in Uyo Metropolis.				
2	Search engine optimization (SEO) improves customer engagement with First Bank Plc’s online platforms.				
3	Search engines drive more online transactions for First Bank Plc.				
4	Search engines enhance the brand awareness of First Bank Plc among potential customers in Uyo Metropolis.				
	Content Marketing				
5	First Bank’s content marketing strategies help increase the visibility of First Bank Plc in Uyo Metropolis.				
6	First Bank’s content marketing efforts enhance customer engagement with First Bank Plc’s online platforms.				
7	First Bank’s cContent marketing strategies drive more online transactions for First Bank Plc.				
8	First Bank’s cContent marketing initiatives help build stronger brand awareness for First Bank Plc in Uyo Metropolis.				
	Marketing Performance				
9	I often discover First Bank’s products and services through search engine results				
10	I am more likely to patronize First Bank after reading their value-driven content online.				
11	I have recommended First Bank to others after engaging with their social media posts.				

12	I have returned to use First Bank's services after receiving follow-up emails.				
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APPENDIX 2

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	14	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	14	100.0

Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.668	20

APPENDIX 3

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	88.178	1	88.178	476.638	.000 ^b
	Residual	11.843	312	0.185		
	Total	100.021	313			

a. Dependent Variable: Market_Perfor.

b. Predictors: (Constant), Search_Engine_Mark.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.798	.276		6.521	.000
	Search_Engine_Mark.	.777	.0068	.677	8.532	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Market_Perfor.

Appendix 4

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	49.445	1	49.445	62.587	.000 ^b
	Residual	50.576	312	.790		
	Total	100.021	313			

a. Dependent Variable: Market_Perfor.

b. Predictors: (Constant), Conte_Marke

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.570	.089		6.430	.000
	Conte_Marke	.766	.021	.822	12.827	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Market_Perfor.